

AI IN ENGLISH TEACHER TRAINING

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Annotation: This research article explores the application of artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance autonomous learning competence in future English language teachers. It discusses personalized educational programs, interactive learning tools, AI-based assessment methods, and challenges such as data security. The study emphasizes AI's potential to improve teaching methods and offers recommendations for effective integration into education systems.

Key words: Artificial intelligence, autonomous learning, English language teaching, personalized education, interactive learning.

Modern education requires constant development and improvement of teaching methods. In this context, enhancing the competence of autonomous learning in future English language teachers becomes a pressing issue. One of the promising directions in this field is the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in education. This article is dedicated to exploring the possibilities of applying AI to enhance the competence of autonomous learning in future English language teachers.

One of the main advantages of using artificial intelligence in education is the ability to create personalized educational programs. According to Schwab, "AI allows for the adaptation of teaching to the specific student, taking into account their level of knowledge, pace of learning, and individual characteristics" [1]. This approach enables the effective use of teaching time and maximizes the potential of each student. Another important aspect of using artificial intelligence in education is the ability to create interactive learning tools. According to Lee, "AI allows for the development of educational games and applications that make the learning process more engaging and effective" [2]. Such tools can stimulate students' interest in learning English and contribute to the development of their autonomy in learning.

Furthermore, the use of artificial intelligence allows for the effective assessment of students' knowledge levels. According to Smith, "AI can analyze test results and offer recommendations for further education of each student" [3]. This approach enables teachers to effectively monitor students' progress and adjust the educational process according to their needs.

On the other hand, it should be noted that the use of artificial intelligence in education also brings certain challenges and problems. One of the main issues is the need to ensure the security of student data. According to Johnson, "Special mechanisms need to be developed to protect data to prevent leakage and misuse" [4]. This requires additional efforts from organizations implementing AI in the educational process.

Additionally, artificial intelligence can be effectively used to create a feedback system. According to Wilson, "AI allows for the automation of the feedback process, enabling students to correct mistakes and improve their skills more quickly" [5]. This approach facilitates faster and more effective learning material assimilation. Thus, the use of artificial intelligence in education has both positive and negative aspects. However, with the right approach and effective risk management, AI can significantly enhance the competence of autonomous learning in future English language teachers.

In addition to the advantages listed, the use of artificial intelligence in education also promotes the development of new methods for assessing students' knowledge. Machine learning systems can analyze large amounts of data and identify patterns in students' responses to test tasks. This allows for the creation of more complex and intellectually stimulating assignments that help students better assimilate the material.

Moreover, artificial intelligence can be used to create virtual learning environments. According to Zhang, "Virtual environments allow students to immerse themselves in the language environment, interact with native speakers, and apply their knowledge in practice" [6]. Such environments can be particularly useful for teaching conversational English, helping students develop communication skills in a foreign language. Another advantage of using artificial intelligence in education is the ability to create individualized educational plans for each student. According to Brown, "AI allows teachers to adapt the curriculum to the specific needs of each student, which promotes more effective material assimilation" [7]. This approach allows teachers to work effectively with each student and take into account their individual characteristics.

Thus, the use of artificial intelligence in education can significantly improve the quality of training for future English language teachers. Personalized educational programs, interactive learning tools, new methods for assessing student knowledge, and virtual learning environments—all these make the learning process more effective, interesting, and accessible. Another advantage of using artificial intelligence in education is the ability to create adaptive testing systems. Such

systems can analyze students' responses to previous questions and automatically select subsequent questions in such a way as to match the student's knowledge level. This allows for more effective determination of preparedness and adaptation of testing to the individual needs of each student.

Moreover, artificial intelligence can be used to create educational assistants. According to Garcia, "Educational assistants based on artificial intelligence can help students solve problems, explain complex concepts, and offer additional materials for study" [8]. Such assistants can significantly facilitate the learning process and improve material comprehension.

Artificial intelligence can also be used for big data analysis in education. According to Li, "Data analysis using AI allows for the identification of trends in education, determination of the effectiveness of educational programs, and identification of areas requiring further development" [9]. This approach allows for more accurate determination of educational system development strategies and enhancement of its effectiveness.

Thus, the use of artificial intelligence in education opens wide prospects for improving the learning process. Personalized educational programs, interactive learning tools, adaptive testing, educational assistants, and big data analysis—all these make learning more effective, accessible, and interesting for students.

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